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STUDYING THE FEATURES OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: The level of development of the agricultural sector and the food market has always been and continues to be a determining factor in economic and socio-political stability in the country, economic and food security, therefore, the dynamic development of this sector of the economy should become one of the main priorities of the state's socio-economic policy for the future. It is no coincidence that food security is an integral part of the country's national security, since no state can achieve national, including economic security, without satisfying, first of all, the population's needs for quality food. The purpose of this article is to consider the digitalization of the agricultural sector and its features in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Innovation, application, scientific developments, production, fertilizers, additives, management system, enterprise, approaches, electronic control.

Annotatsiya: Qishloq xo'jaligi va oziq-ovqat bozorining rivojlanish darajasi mamlakatimizdagi iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy-siyosiy barqarorlikni, iqtisodiy va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashda doimo hal qiluvchi omil bo'lib kelgan va bo'lib qolmoqda, shuning uchun iqtisodiyotning ushbu tarmog'ini jadal rivojlantirish zarur. Istiqboldagi davlat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy siyosatining asosiy ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biriga aylanishi. Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi mamlakat milliy xavfsizligining ajralmas qismi ekanligi bejiz emas, chunki hech bir davlat, birinchi navbatda, aholining sifatli oziq-ovqatga bo'lgan ehtiyojini qondirmasdan turib milliy, jumladan, iqtisodiy xavfsizlikka erisha olmaydi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligini raqamlashtirish va uning xususiyatlarini ko'rib chiqishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: Innovatsiya, qo'llash, ilmiy ishlanmalar, ishlab chiqarish, o'g'itlar, qo'shimchalar, boshqaruv tizimi, korxonalar, yondashuvlar, elektron boshqaruv.

Аннотация: Уровень развития аграрного сектора и продовольственного рынка всегда был и продолжает оставаться определяющим фактором экономической и социально-политической стабильности в стране, экономической и продовольственной безопасности, поэтому динамичное развитие этого сектора экономики должно стать одним из главных приоритетов социально-экономической политики государства на перспективу. Неслучайно продовольственная безопасность является неотъемлемой частью национальной безопасности страны, поскольку ни одно государство не может достичь национальной, в том числе экономической безопасности, не удовлетворив, прежде всего, потребности населения в качественных продуктах питания. Целью данной статьи является рассмотрение цифровизации аграрного сектора и ее особенностей в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: Инновации, применение, научные разработки, производство, удобрения, добавки, система управления, предприятие, подходы, электронное управление.

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector throughout the history of our country has played an important role in the Uzbek economy. The market transformations carried out in our country led to a revision of the scientific concepts of the development of the agrarian economy. The rethinking of organizational and economic relations in the agrarian sector has acquired significant scientific significance, which has led to institutional changes in agricultural production.

The formation of new institutions that meet market requirements was uneven and contradictory, because the formation of the most significant guidelines and vectors for the reorganization of the institutions of the administrative-command system was not given due attention by the reformers. The agricultural sector dominates the economy of most countries in the world. In Uzbekistan, as in many other countries with a rapidly developing economy, the topic of the country's food security has been and continues to be a topical issue.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The agro-industrial sector of the national economy occupies a particularly important place in economic theory today. There are a number of important points that necessitate a large-scale study of current trends in the development of the agricultural market in our country.

The innovative development of the Uzbek agricultural sector is one of the most important factors in increasing the competitiveness of the national economy in the world market. At present, the technical, technological, scientific, managerial level of the vast majority of Uzbek agricultural producers does not allow reaching the level of productivity, for example, of the EU countries or the USA. This also applies to labor productivity, the level of which in Uzbekistan is several times lower than that of Western competitors. After Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO, there was an increase in the level of competition in the domestic food market of the country, and by the end of the "transitional" period, it will be difficult for domestic producers of certain types of agricultural products to compete with imports. The solution in such a situation can be a systematic comprehensive transition to the introduction of innovations in various areas of agricultural production – from raw materials to management systems. Innovative activity in agriculture is a set of consistent actions to create new or improve agricultural products, develop technologies, management systems based on the application of research developments or production experience. New technologies are a combination of certain forms and methods of teaching, to offer students a solution to the problem of an educational task as a result of independent action [5, 35].

Innovations in Uzbek agriculture can be divided into several groups [1, 10].

Firstly, these are innovations associated with wear and tear or severe obsolescence of agricultural machinery. Although these investments may seem devoid of innovation, this is the case for a large part of the country's agricultural holdings. Therefore, the introduction of technology, which is used everywhere in Western countries, in Uzbek reality can be considered a "regional" innovation.

Secondly, the innovation will be the introduction of elite plant varieties, as well as highly productive breeds into production.

Thirdly, innovation can be in the application of scientific developments to stimulate production, that is, new fertilizers and additives in various areas of agriculture.

Fourth, innovation can affect the management system of an enterprise – from new approaches to management to the introduction of electronic control and production management systems.

Fifth, innovations may relate to the infrastructure of the agro-industrial complex, which is related to macroeconomic decisions and requires the attention and support of the state. These can be measures to assess the state of soils and recommendations to farmers, consultations on the introduction of certain innovations in production, information about various developments and opportunities. Or it can be programs for the rental of highly productive agricultural machinery by small and medium-sized enterprises from the state. The gradual and balanced application of all these types of innovation in practice can have a positive effect on the agro-industrial complex of Uzbekistan as a whole.

Innovative activity in Uzbek agriculture has its own characteristics [2, 9]:

First, the peculiarity of the final product in relation to other industries is obvious – food. That is, the use of any innovation should be aimed not only at economic benefits, but also at ensuring the health of consumers. At the same time, the quality of the product or possible harm to the consumer is often impossible to assess in a short-term examination, and the negative effect can only appear after a long period of consumption (a notable example is the cultivation of GMO products). Secondly, the introduction of innovations in agriculture has temporary features. Since food production is largely related to seasonality, in order to assess the impact of certain innovations on the final product, it takes time for the product to be grown and processed. Since this process takes several months and the re-testing of innovations is possible only in the next season, which makes the evaluation of the effectiveness of innovation long in time. This is especially noticeable in crop production and in animal husbandry, in which the cycle exceeds 1 year. At the same time, there are areas of agriculture, such as dairy farming or horticulture, where the time period for assessing innovation can take 5-10 years.

The third feature is related to the second and lies in the long payback period of innovations, which is one of the main constraints on the way of their implementation in private enterprises. In addition, this factor strongly depends on the development of the institution of private property: if the state is unable to ensure the inviolability of ownership of land or the means of production, then long-term investments in the acquisition of innovative technologies from the entrepreneur should not be expected.

The fourth feature is the variety of agricultural products. Small and medium-sized farms are forced to produce a wide range of different products in order to support demand, as well as reduce their risks from crop failures or market fluctuations. In this regard, the development of innovative technologies should take this factor into account in order to be beneficial to various manufacturers and have a wide scope.

The fifth feature is the unpredictability of weather and natural conditions, on which productivity and production technology often depend. Independence from weather conditions is one of the most demanded areas of innovative development associated with the breeding of more resistant varieties and breeds. The sixth feature is the need to adapt plants and animals to various territorial climatic conditions. This factor is especially relevant for Uzbekistan, where the variety of climatic zones is wide. Which indicates the need for a local approach to the development of innovations, as well as to building a mechanism for introducing innovations in agriculture and state policy aimed at stimulating innovations in the agro-industrial complex [3, 21].

The seventh feature is that neighboring agricultural enterprises in Uzbekistan are often quite far from each other, due to the large territory of the country. Therefore, if the technology being implemented requires investments in equipment, then the remoteness will prevent the possibility of sharing it. Small farms have to have a wide specialization, so they have to keep inefficient universal equipment, and investing in specialized equipment is beyond their strength.

The eighth feature is the low level of training of agro-industrial workers that has developed in Uzbekistan, which necessitates special attention to the process of training and training personnel when introducing innovations, since due to poor-quality application, even an effective technology may not give a result.

The ninth feature of innovation activity in the agro-industrial complex of Uzbekistan is the lack of established links between the vast majority of producers. And this applies to both agricultural producers and manufacturers of related industries, including those aimed at the production of innovative products in terms of agricultural engineering, fertilizer production, seed breeding, as well as elite breeds of animals. At the same time, in Uzbekistan there is no well-established mechanism for the introduction of scientific and technical developments into production. This leads to the fact that the level of innovation in Uzbek agriculture remains at an extremely low level. At present, the main investments in Uzbek agriculture go to the restoration of fixed assets due to their natural wear and tear. A significant share of investments in innovations can be observed only in certain industries – cattle breeding, poultry farming, as well as growing vegetables in greenhouses. This imbalance is explained by the fact that the reproduction cycle in these industries is much lower than in other areas of agriculture, for example, in broiler production, the cycle is 1.5 months, in pig breeding – 3-4 months. And at the same time, they do not strongly depend on either the seasonal factor or the weather and climate, which makes it possible to recoup investments in innovation fairly quickly. As well, business – oriented approach [4, 31].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When developing and implementing innovations, one should take into account the fact that different agricultural producers are at different technological levels of their production. The level of introduction of mechanization, the share of manual labor, capital intensity, resource intensity varies from small farms to large agricultural holdings. At present, information resources are increasingly affecting both the product produced by the enterprise and changes in the organization's fixed assets. For example, the introduction of GLONASS technology into tractors has allowed many farms to save significantly and improve the quality of land cultivation. The introduction of such information technologies can increase the level of control, the productivity of basic resources and labor productivity. The growth of information technology leads to the fact that the role of the manufacturer's reputation increases, since it becomes difficult to hide the poor quality of the goods or the unscrupulous attitude towards the environment in the production area. Therefore, the role of innovation in fixed assets to improve the environmental friendliness of production is increasing. The use of innovative technologies in the information society can be a significant marketing advantage in a competitive market, as it will cause greater trust and respect for the manufacturer. The introduction of innovations in the field of energy saving is also coming to the fore in agriculture. Energy prices continue to rise and occupy an increasing share in the cost structure of agricultural products. Compared to agricultural producers in other CIS countries, Uzbek production is 5 times more energy-intensive, 4 times more material-intensive, and labor productivity is 8–10 times lower. At the same time, the process of introducing innovations in these countries takes place on a constant market basis. The states of these countries have created a mechanism that encourages enterprises to introduce innovations, thereby making the rejection of innovations economically unprofitable.

CONCLUSIONS

The reality is that the rural social sphere remains underdeveloped in many respects, and it is this underdevelopment that affects the quality of rural labor, pushing rural youth to exodus to the cities. Ultimately, the lack of rural human capital limits economic growth in our country, causing some skepticism about the possibility of achieving the goals set by the Uzbek leadership in terms of strengthening the international agricultural competitiveness of Uzbekistan.

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“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
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